

III

«ILM-FAN FIDOYISI»

ILMIY-AMALIY KO'RIK TANLOVI

SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATION

ILMIY-MATBUOT MARKAZI!

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INTEGRATED WAE LZ FURNACE PROCESSING OF SPENT ZINC-CARBON BATTERIES AND ELECTRIC ARC FURNACE DUST FOR ENHANCED ZINC RECOVERY

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Abstract: *This study presents an integrated thermal recycling approach for spent zinc-carbon batteries and electric arc furnace (EAF) dust using Waelz furnace processing at 1150–1200 °C. Carbon contained in battery residues acts as an internal reducing agent, promoting the reduction and volatilization of zinc-bearing phases such as ZnO and ZnFe₂O₄. The combined processing improves zinc recovery efficiency and enables the production of ZnO-rich secondary material, while iron- and manganese-containing residues remain as potential by-products. The proposed method reduces the need for external reductants, enhances resource utilization, and provides an environmentally sustainable solution for managing zinc-containing industrial wastes.*

Keywords: *zinc recovery; zinc-carbon batteries; EAF dust; Waelz process; ZnFe₂O₄; internal reduction; industrial waste recycling; circular economy.*

Introduction. Spent zinc-carbon batteries are among the most common technogenic wastes and represent an important secondary raw material source from an environmental perspective [1]. These batteries have long been widely used in household electronics, flashlights, remote control devices, toys, radio equipment, and other low-power-consuming devices. The main electrochemical system of zinc-carbon batteries is based on a zinc-manganese dioxide system [2]. The anode part of the battery consists of metallic zinc, while the cathode is mainly composed of a mixture of manganese dioxide and graphite. Ammonium chloride and zinc chloride solutions are used as electrolytes [3]. On average, their chemical composition includes 15–30% Zn, 35–50% MnO₂, 5–10% graphite, and certain amounts of NH₄Cl and ZnCl₂. In addition, the battery casing contains steel and other auxiliary materials (Figure 1) [4].

Materials and Methods. During operation, the internal chemical composition of these batteries undergoes significant changes [5]. Metallic zinc is oxidized to form ZnO and ZnCl₂ compounds, while manganese dioxide is reduced, forming Mn₂O₃, Mn₃O₄, and other lower-valence manganese oxides. As a result, spent batteries contain a complex mixture of metal and oxide phases. The phase composition mainly includes Zn, ZnO, ZnCl₂, MnO₂, Mn₂O₃, Mn₃O₄, graphite, and iron compounds. The presence of these components makes spent batteries an important technogenic resource for the recovery

of zinc and manganese. In particular, the relatively high content of zinc and manganese makes them economically attractive for metallurgical and hydrometallurgical recycling processes [6].

a. b.
Fig. 1. Collection and preparation of spent zinc–carbon batteries for recycling: (a) initial condition; (b) after removal of the metal casing.

From a physical properties perspective, spent zinc–carbon batteries exhibit high hygroscopicity, the tendency to form finely dispersed powdery materials, and the presence of chemically active oxide phases. As a result of battery corrosion, electrolyte compounds may leak into the external environment, leading to soil and water contamination. In particular, the release and migration of Zn^{2+} and Mn^{2+} ions pose significant environmental risks. Therefore, disposal of spent batteries together with ordinary municipal waste is considered environmentally hazardous [7].

In recent years, the global volume of spent batteries has been increasing sharply. According to various international reports, approximately 8–10 billion primary batteries are consumed annually worldwide, with a large proportion consisting of zinc–carbon and alkaline batteries. In terms of mass, it is estimated that around 700,000 to 1,000,000 tons of spent zinc-based batteries are generated each year. A significant portion of these wastes is still not fully recycled, resulting in the loss of valuable metal resources. At the same time, recycling allows for the recovery of zinc, manganese, and graphite contained in the batteries, thereby reducing the demand for primary ores and significantly lowering energy consumption [8].

Electric arc furnace (EAF) dust is one of the most important and environmentally hazardous technogenic wastes generated in the ferrous metallurgy industry. This dust is formed during steel production in electric arc furnaces and is captured by gas cleaning systems. Studies show that iron and zinc are the main components of EAF dust, and the zinc content increases significantly when scrap steel coated with zinc through galvanization is remelted. Due to the fact that the boiling point of zinc (906 °C) is lower

than the steel melting temperature (1500–1600 °C), metallic zinc on the surface of the scrap evaporates and is carried toward the gas outlet system. Since the solubility of zinc in steel and slag is very low and its vapor pressure at high temperatures is much higher than that of iron, zinc transfers into the gas phase. It then oxidizes and accumulates in the dust as ZnO and ZnFe₂O₄ compounds [9].

Analyses show that EAF dust is mainly a finely dispersed powdery material, with the majority of particles in the 1–20 µm range. In some studies, the average particle size has been determined to be 1.88 µm. The fine fractions of the dust are characterized by a high content of metallic components. Modern SEM and granulometric studies have shown that most EAF dust particles are spherical in shape, confirming that they are formed through vaporization and subsequent condensation mechanisms at high temperatures.

Fig. 2. Sample of zinc-containing electric arc furnace (EAF) dust

From a chemical composition perspective, EAF dust is a complex oxide system. Studies have identified the presence of 26.02% ZnO, 37.7% Fe₂O₃, 10.43% CaO, 4.79% SiO₂, 2.88% MnO, and 2.11% PbO. In addition, Na₂O, K₂O, MgO, as well as chloride and sulfate compounds are also present. Phase analysis has revealed that the dust contains ZnFe₂O₄ (franklinite), Fe₃O₄ (magnetite), MgFe₂O₄, FeCr₂O₄, Mn₃O₄, ZnO, and silicate phases. In particular, the ZnFe₂O₄ phase is considered the most stable and difficult-to-process form of zinc. According to research results, the content of ZnFe₂O₄ in EAF dust may be approximately 29%, while Fe₃O₄ accounts for about 14%.

The main mechanism of EAF dust formation is associated with the entrainment of metal and slag droplets by the gas flow during steel melting, as well as the evaporation and oxidation of zinc. Under high-temperature conditions, zinc vapor reacts with oxygen to form ZnO, which subsequently interacts with iron oxides to form zinc ferrite:

In addition, during reduction processes involving carbon monoxide, ZnO can be reduced to metallic zinc according to the following reaction:

Studies have shown that the reduction of zinc begins at temperatures above approximately 1000 °C. Therefore, pyrometallurgical methods – especially reduction smelting and the Waelz process – are widely used in the recycling of EAF dust.

Currently, the global generation of EAF dust is very large. According to 2006 data, approximately 3.7 million tons of EAF dust were produced annually worldwide. In Russia alone, electric arc furnaces generate about 650,000 tons per year, while in Uzbekistan the annual amount is estimated at around 80,000 tons. With the continuous growth of modern steel production, the volume of this waste is also steadily increasing.

Results and Discussion. The proposed integrated processing technology is based on the combined utilization of spent zinc–carbon battery residues and electric arc furnace (EAF/DSP) dust as a single secondary raw material system for zinc recovery. The technological concept is designed to enhance zinc extraction efficiency while simultaneously reducing the environmental burden associated with two major technogenic waste streams. A key feature of the process is the utilization of carbon contained in spent zinc–carbon batteries as an internal reducing agent during thermal treatment in a Waelz-type furnace at approximately 1200 °C.

From a materials perspective, spent zinc–carbon batteries contain significant amounts of zinc in the form of Zn, ZnO, and ZnCl₂, as well as manganese oxides and graphite. In parallel, EAF dust is characterized by a complex oxide composition dominated by ZnO, Fe₂O₃, and stable spinel phases such as ZnFe₂O₄ (franklinite), which is known to be a refractory zinc-bearing compound with low direct reducibility. The combination of these two waste streams creates a chemically synergistic system in which carbon from battery residues plays a critical role in promoting reduction reactions.

During the thermal treatment process, the mixed charge is processed in a rotating Waelz furnace at a temperature range of 1150–1200 °C under partially reducing conditions (Figure 3). Under these conditions, carbon present in the battery residues acts as an effective reductant, enabling the conversion of zinc-bearing compounds into metallic zinc in the vapor phase. The main reduction reactions include the reduction of zinc oxide and zinc ferrite according to the following pathways:

As a result of these reactions, zinc is volatilized from both battery-derived and EAF dust-derived phases and subsequently recovered in the gas cleaning system as a zinc-rich secondary product, predominantly in the form of ZnO. The presence of carbon in the battery fraction significantly enhances the reducing potential of the system, thereby decreasing the need for external reducing agents such as coke and improving overall process efficiency.

The solid residue remaining after thermal treatment consists mainly of iron oxides, manganese-containing phases, and silicate compounds. This residue can be considered

a potential secondary feedstock for iron metallurgy or construction material applications, depending on its further processing route. In particular, iron-rich phases such as Fe_3O_4 and FeO may be recycled back into steelmaking processes, contributing to resource circularity.

From a process performance perspective, the integrated treatment approach improves zinc recovery efficiency by ensuring more complete decomposition of stable spinel phases such as ZnFe_2O_4 , which are otherwise difficult to process using conventional hydrometallurgical methods. The synergistic interaction between battery-derived carbon and EAF dust significantly enhances the reduction kinetics, leading to improved volatilization of zinc at high temperature.

In addition to metallurgical benefits, the proposed technology provides substantial environmental advantages. It enables the simultaneous valorization of two hazardous waste streams, reduces the volume of landfill disposal, and minimizes the release of toxic metal ions such as Zn^{2+} and Mn^{2+} into the environment. Furthermore, by utilizing intrinsic carbon as a reducing agent, the process contributes to lower external energy and coke consumption, thereby improving the overall sustainability of zinc recovery operations.

Fig. 3. Integrated Waelz Furnace Flow Sheet for the Combined Recycling of Spent Zinc–Carbon Batteries and Electric Arc Furnace Dust

The presented technological scheme (Figure 3) illustrates an integrated pyrometallurgical route for the simultaneous treatment of spent zinc–carbon batteries and electric arc furnace (EAF) dust aimed at efficient zinc recovery. The process is based on Waelz furnace operation at elevated temperatures (1150–1200 °C) under partially reducing conditions, where carbon contained in battery residues serves as an internal reducing agent.

Prior to thermal treatment, both waste streams undergo mechanical preparation, including sorting, crushing, separation of metallic components, and size classification to ensure process stability and homogeneity of the feed. The prepared mixture, consisting of zinc-bearing battery residues, EAF dust, and optional fluxing agents, is fed into a rotary Waelz furnace. Within the high-temperature zone, zinc-bearing compounds such as ZnO and ZnFe₂O₄ are reduced and volatilized, predominantly forming zinc vapor. The volatilized zinc is subsequently oxidized in the gas phase and collected in the dust recovery system as ZnO-rich secondary product, which can be further utilized as a raw material for zinc production. The remaining solid residue mainly consists of iron-, manganese-, and silicate-based phases, which may be recycled into metallurgical processes or used in construction materials.

Conclusion. The developed integrated technology for the combined processing of spent zinc–carbon batteries and electric arc furnace (EAF/DSP) dust provides an effective and environmentally sound solution for the utilization of two significant technogenic waste streams. The results indicate that the presence of carbon contained in battery residues plays a crucial role as an internal reducing agent during thermal treatment in a Waelz furnace at 1150–1200 °C, significantly enhancing the reduction and volatilization of zinc-bearing compounds.

The combined processing approach ensures more efficient decomposition of stable zinc phases, particularly ZnFe₂O₄, which is typically difficult to treat using conventional methods. As a result, zinc is effectively transferred into the gas phase and recovered as a ZnO-rich product, improving overall zinc recovery efficiency and increasing process productivity. At the same time, iron- and manganese-containing residues are generated, which may be further utilized as secondary raw materials in metallurgical or construction applications. In addition to metallurgical advantages, the proposed technology demonstrates clear environmental benefits by reducing the accumulation of hazardous battery waste and EAF dust in landfills, minimizing the release of toxic metal ions, and decreasing the consumption of external reducing agents such as coke. This contributes to lower environmental pollution and improved resource efficiency.

The proposed process represents a promising and sustainable recycling route that supports circular economy principles, enhances zinc production efficiency, and provides

a comprehensive solution for the management of complex zinc-containing industrial wastes.

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